

Workshop: AI - ally or enemy for engineering learning?

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Abstract

The last few years have seen the irruption of artificial intelligence for a multitude of applications. The speed of development of such applications has been faster than the speed of adaptation to them in the field of university education. Given this fact, the question arises as to whether to prohibit the use of AI by students as their learning may be negatively affected (something equivalent to cheating) or to allow (or promote) its use. In the first case it is possible that students will use AI and try to hide it. In the second case, it will be necessary to adapt the learning activities so that their outcomes are not compromised. In the proposed hands-on session these issues will be discussed as well as how to approach the design of learning activities that reinforce learning by promoting the use of AI tools.

Keywords: AI in engineering education; Active learning in engineering education.

1 Introduction

In the ever-evolving landscape of education, it is incumbent upon us as educators to adapt our teaching methodologies to meet the needs and expectations of the next generation of engineers. As we witness the transformative power of Artificial Intelligence (AI) across various domains, it becomes imperative for us to explore its potential applications in engineering education. The forthcoming workshop serves as a platform for us to collectively delve into this crucial intersection and strategize on how we can leverage AI to reinforce and enrich students' learning experiences.

The objective of this workshop is not merely to introduce AI as a novelty in our classrooms but rather to comprehensively examine how AI tools and techniques can be seamlessly integrated into our pedagogical approaches to amplify student engagement, comprehension, and retention of engineering concepts. Through collaborative discussions, interactive sessions, and hands-on demonstrations, we aim to equip the participants with the knowledge, resources, and strategies necessary to effectively harness AI for the betterment of engineering education.

Allowing engineering students to use AI tools for their tasks comes with several strengths and potential dangers:

Strengths:

1. *Efficiency and Productivity:* AI tools can automate repetitive tasks, allowing students to focus more on problem-solving and creative aspects of engineering projects.
2. *Enhanced Learning Experience:* By using AI tools, students can gain hands-on experience with cutting-edge technologies relevant to their field.
3. *Personalized Learning:* AI tools can adapt to individual learning styles and preferences, providing personalized feedback and recommendations to students.
4. *Access to Advanced Technologies:* This democratization of technology can level the playing field and empower students from diverse backgrounds.

5. *Fostering Innovation*: By leveraging AI tools, students can explore innovative solutions to complex problems and push the boundaries of traditional engineering practices.

Dangers:

1. *Overreliance on AI*: There is a risk that students may become overly dependent on AI tools, relying on them to perform tasks without fully understanding the underlying principle.
2. *Bias and Ethics Concerns*: AI algorithms may inherit biases from the data they are trained on, leading to biased outcomes or decisions. Moreover, the ethical implications of using AI in engineering tasks, such as privacy concerns or unintended consequences, need to be carefully considered and addressed.
3. *Skills Gap*: Depending too heavily on AI tools without developing foundational engineering skills could result in a skills gap among students.
4. *Security Risks*: AI tools may introduce security vulnerabilities or privacy risks, particularly if they involve handling sensitive data or interacting with external systems.
5. *Loss of Creativity and Innovation*: While AI can facilitate innovation, there is a concern that it may also stifle creativity by limiting the diversity of solutions explored or by imposing constraints based on existing data patterns.

Overall, while the integration of AI tools in engineering education offers numerous benefits, it is essential to approach their use thoughtfully and mitigate potential dangers through proper guidance, ethical considerations, and a holistic approach to learning. This is, in essence, the main objective of the proposed workshop.

According to Mhlanga (2023) “the use of ChatGPT in education requires (...) transparency in the use of ChatGPT”, so it is fair to admit that the above text, as a sample of the potential of using AI tools, was mostly written in response to a single ChatGPT prompt. Strength number 1 is obvious, both in terms of time efficiency and writing style (which is a major effort for people for whom English is not their mother tongue). However, although we do not have concrete data, the first appreciations about the impact of the use of this tool by students generate certain problems, especially the lack of reflection, due to the immediate obtaining of results, and, more importantly, the loss of learning opportunities by not having to face the search for error solution inherent to the problem-solving process.

It may seem reasonable to decide in a thoughtful way, what access to AI there should be for engineering education in the future (actually, already in the present). According to Cárdenas (2023) we can think in, to simplify, four scenarios (Figure 1).

		possible future scenarios	
		Training and adaptation by teaching staff	
		Low	High
Access to AI	High	Eternal 2023 The student uses it and hides it Inequality among students	AI for everyone Teacher + Assitant IA + Tutor IA Student more involved in learning
	Low	Back to 2019 A few (elite) use it Inequality between universities	IA for me Teacher uses it, student does not Teacher-dependent students

Figure 1. Possible future scenarios about the use of AI in education.

Although the risks of regenerative AI have been identified in several studies, such as Cain (2023), Moloji et al (2023) or Qadir (2023), the solution does not seem to be to prohibit its use. Moreover, we know without a doubt that its use is widespread among students. Trying to prevent its use makes the same sense as thinking that a calculator or a spell checker could be banned. In addition, as has become clear from the beginning of this introduction, educators use generative AI to, among other things, increase productivity.

Here's what you can expect from this workshop (also generated by chatGPT):

Designing AI-Enhanced Learning Activities and Assessments: we will delve into the practical aspects of designing AI-enhanced learning activities and assessments.

Addressing Challenges and Ethical Considerations: As with any technological innovation, the integration of AI into engineering education presents its own set of challenges and ethical considerations. We will facilitate discussions on topics such as data privacy, algorithmic bias, and the ethical use of AI, empowering you to navigate these complexities and cultivate a responsible AI culture within your classrooms.

Fostering a Community of AI-Enabled Educators: Finally, this workshop serves as an opportunity for you to connect with fellow educators who share a passion for leveraging AI to enhance student learning in engineering. Through collaborative brainstorming and networking, you will have the chance to exchange ideas, share best practices, and forge meaningful partnerships that extend beyond the confines of this workshop.

2 Activities

As stated in the introduction, the objective of the workshop is to discuss, explore and analyse the potential risks of generative AI as a tool for learners and to seek strategies to minimize such risks in the design of learning activities that strengthen learning outcomes. Attendants will be arranged in small groups making emphasis in forming teams with people with different background. The session will be organized as follows:

- Topic presentation.
- Warm-up activity.
- Risk identification.
- Search for activity design strategies.
- Discussion.
- Conclusion.

As the discussion on the responsible and ethical usage of ChatGPT in education has been encouraged (Mhlanga, 2023) a special focus will be placed on this extremely important topic. **Participants must provide a laptop or cell phone.**

3 Expected results

After the workshop, it is expected that attendees will have a clear idea of the potential risks of AI in their respective courses. It is also expected that they will have come up with activity design strategies to minimize such risks. It will be interesting to know if participants find the proposal interesting enough and to listen to their comment to make the activity more interesting and productive for possible future editions.

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